

POLITICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF RELATIONS BETWEEN KAZAKHSTAN AND KYRGYZSTAN FROM A COMMERCIAL AND ECONOMIC POINT OF VIEW

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Abstract

The Republic of Kazakhstan and the Kyrgyz Republic have always been close friends, allies and brotherly countries. In the past decades, a solid foundation of bilateral relations has been laid. In recent years, various meetings have been held to strengthen the relations of Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. The status and appearance of the commercial and economic relations of the two countries are regularly discussed at the level of diplomatic representatives, including the heads of state and government of the two countries, the foreign ministers, the ministers of the relevant fields and the ambassadors. Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan have successfully interacted within the framework of international and regional organizations and have the same or close positions in many important international and regional issues. This completes the current interaction potential of the two countries. Today, one of the main objectives of foreign policy of both countries is the dynamic and balanced development of foreign economic ties, which provide the most favorable conditions for economic growth. In this context, the expansion of the commercial and economic cooperation is of particular importance for the two republics. The trade and economic relations between the two states are analyzed below.

Keywords: Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, commercial relations, economic relations, trade, export, import

Kazakhstan is the second largest export market for Kyrgyzstan after Switzerland. The money from Kazakhstan traditionally plays an important role in the economy of Kyrgyzstan. It should be noted that the excess of exports over imports has been maintained since 1995 to the present. Exports decreased by 15.7%, from \$518.6 million in 2015 to \$437.2 million in 2016. Imports increased by 27.1%, from \$182.0 million in 2015 to \$231.4 million in 2016. [1]

The main export goods supplied from Kazakhstan to Kyrgyzstan are: petroleum products, tobacco products, wheat, rolled products made of non-enriched steel, flat, mineral and carbonated water, sugar, coal, hot-rolled steel made of non-enriched steel, automobiles, hygiene products for women and children, cement. The main types of imported goods from Kyrgyzstan to Kazakhstan are: other ores and concentrates, petroleum products, polished glass, bakery and flour confectionery, milk and cream not condensed, plastic containers, alcohol, butter, yogurt, kefir. [2]

Trade is primarily a basic type of interaction between people and countries. The main volume of exports is provided by such sectors of the economy as agriculture, animal husbandry and the domestic flagship of the economy, light industry. Kazakh entrepreneurs are quite actively showing their desire to cooperate with their Kyrgyz colleagues. Kazakhstani businessmen are interested in cooperation in the field of light industry, agricultural products, the products of tanneries, i.e. the raw materials themselves. [3]

Currently, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan are planning to increase their trade volume to \$ 2 billion. For example, according to the press service of the President of the Kazakhstan Council of Ministers, during a meeting held in April 2022 between the Prime Minister of Kazakhstan Alihan Smayilov and the Ambassador of Kyrgyzstan Dastan Dushekeyev, the parties discussed

cooperation in the fields of trade, investment, transit and transportation, as well as water-energy balance. While discussing the issue of mutual trade, the Prime Minister expressed his opinion on the need to expand the product range. The most important achievement in the field of trade and economics was the increase in mutual trade volume and the achievement of the trade volume target of 1 billion dollars. The new target is to reach a trade turnover of 2 billion dollars. [4]

During his official visit to Bishkek on the invitation of Sadyr Japarov in May 2022, President of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev used the following statements about increasing the trade volume between the two countries to \$ 2 billion: "Today I am in Bishkek at the invitation of President Sadyr Japarov. We have agreed to increase the trade volume between our countries to \$ 2 billion in the coming years. In order to achieve these goals, we need to create conditions for the entrepreneurs of our countries, this also applies to integration". During his meeting with President Sadyr Japarov earlier, Kassym-Jomart Tokayev stated that Kazakhstan can sell hundreds of types of goods and products to Kyrgyzstan with the support of KazakhExport. [5]

Today, the business world of the two countries is effectively evaluating mutual trade opportunities. For example, Kazakhstan plans to export 1000 Yutong brand buses to Kyrgyzstan. Within the scope of the visit of the Chairman of the Council of Ministers of Kyrgyzstan Akylbek Japarov to Kazakhstan on December 8, 2021, a memorandum on the purchase of buses was signed at the Government House in Nur-Sultan. According to the press service of the Prime Minister of Kazakhstan, the memorandum provides for the supply of 1,000 Yutong brand electric, gas and diesel buses produced in Kazakhstan and 100 pieces of special equipment to Kyrgyzstan on a leasing basis in 2022. [6]

In addition, six export contracts have been signed for the supply of products worth \$ 17.5 million from Kazakhstan to Kyrgyzstan. In addition, six export contracts were signed for the supply of 17.5 million dollars of products from Kazakhstan to Kyrgyzstan. According to Kazinform International News Agency, which referred to the press service of the Ministry of Trade of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Kazakhstan Trade and Economic Mission (TEM) carried out important work in Bishkek. As a result of the negotiations between Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan enterprises within the scope of TEM, 6 export contracts were signed for the supply of salt, flour and pasta, beer and soft drinks, confectionery and dairy products from Kazakhstan to Kyrgyzstan. The total amount of the contracts made is \$ 17.5 million. [7]

As it can be seen, political dialogues have been continuing since the establishment of diplomatic relations between the two countries, mutual visits and contacts have been carried out at the highest level. These mutual high-level meetings, visits and contacts contribute to the development of trade and economic relations between the two countries. For example, according to the information obtained from the Anadolu Agency website, President of Kyrgyzstan Sadyr Japarov met with President of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev on March 2, 2021, within the framework of his state visit. Tokayev and Japarov discussed bilateral cooperation issues covering trade, economy, investment, defense, energy, water resources, customs, health, education and cultural fields. In addition, documents have been signed between the authorized ministries of the two countries in many areas such as electricity trade. Accordingly, Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan will start implementing cooperation projects in the fields of industry, hydropower, fuel and energy complex, use of underground resources, agriculture, processing sector, logistics and banking. [8]

Currently, it is planned to implement many projects between Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan. For example, it is planned to modernize the Lugovaya-Balykchy railway line between Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan to make it suitable for electric trains. According to the information obtained from the Sputnik.kg website, it has been announced that a new road map for the development of railway transportation in the country was determined by the Prime Ministry of Kyrgyzstan on January 25, 2021, and within the framework of this road map, the Lugovaya-Balykchy railway line between Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan will be equipped with an electrification system between 2023 and 2025. [9]

It is also planned to establish an oil processing facility with the partnership of the two countries. According to the information obtained from the website Economist.kg, Kazakhstan's Temirlan Oil representatives have announced that they are planning to establish an oil processing facility in the Mamak Free Trade Zone in the Talas Region of Kyrgyzstan, and within this framework, a proposal has been submitted to the Kyrgyz authorities. [10]

The relations between the two countries are increasing day by day. For example, during the IX meeting of the Intergovernmental Council held between the

Prime Minister of Kazakhstan Askar Mamin and the Prime Minister of Kyrgyzstan Ulukbek Maripov on April 2, 2021, trade-economic relations, investment, agriculture, water, energy, transit and transportation, tourism, space and informatics, cooperation in the field of industry, education, culture, health, social security, population and labor migration, environmental protection, interregional and border cooperation, Eurasian Economic Union (EEU) and other integration issues were discussed. In addition, the parties evaluated the possibility of establishing the "Alatau" joint border Trade Center at the "Karatuu - Ak Tilek" checkpoint. As part of the project to establish the center, it is planned to create modern warehouses for fruit and vegetable products, as well as certification organizations, sanitary and phytosanitary checkpoints. During the meeting, the construction of wholesale distribution centers in the Chuy and Issyk-Lake regions of Kyrgyzstan was also discussed. After the meeting, the Heads of Government attended the opening ceremony of the "Korday-Ak-Yol" crossing point. Such activities will be able to have a significant impact on the development of trade and economic cooperation between Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan. [11]

Today, Kyrgyzstan-Kazakhstan cooperation has recently gained dynamism and a practical focus. For example, according to the information service of the Ministry of Trade and Integration of Kazakhstan, the government of Kazakhstan is considering building a trade and logistics complex in the regions surrounding four neighboring countries and on the Caspian Sea coast. Accordingly, an industrial trade and logistics complex will be built in the border region of Kyrgyzstan (Jambyl region). Central Asia International Industrial Cooperation Center (Turkestan Region) on the border of Uzbekistan, Eurasia Border Shopping Center (West Kazakhstan Region) on the Russian border, and Caspian Junction container center in Aktau city located on the Caspian Sea coast will be built. In addition, the International Border Cooperation Center Horgos complex on the Chinese border will also be expanded. Trade and logistics complexes carry out the activities of storage, recovery, processing of goods, production of new goods and their effective integration into international goods distribution systems and sales. These complexes reduce the cost of goods and allow them to be delivered quickly to the targeted points. [12]

As it seems, bilateral cooperation between the two countries is increasing day by day. For example, according to the news published on the official website of Economist.kg on May 26, 2022, President of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev announced that after his meeting with his Kyrgyz counterpart, it is planned to establish a solar power plant in the Issyk-Kul region with the participation of Kazakhstan. The cost of the project will be 300 million dollars. Tokayev stressed that Kazakhstan is ready to fully fulfill all its obligations and jointly implement important projects. The President of the Republic of Kazakhstan, during his earlier meeting with the President of Kyrgyzstan Sadyr Japarov, offered to study mutually beneficial proposals and create a list of promising investment projects. [13]

Today, the business world of the two countries actively evaluates investment opportunities. Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan are planning to jointly build a hydroelectric power plant. According to the news of Liter.kz, on January 6, 2023, in Bishkek, the energy ministers of Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan and Kyrgyzstan agreed on the joint construction of Kambar-Ata HEPP-1. After its construction is completed, it is expected that Kambar-Ata HEPP-1 will be the largest power plant in Kyrgyzstan. The HEPP will be able to stabilize the electricity and water supply for the Central Asian countries. [14]

Today, the issues between the two countries are tried to be resolved only with a mutually beneficial and compromising understanding. Cooperation is carried out in accordance with the mutual interests of the parties. For example, during the meeting of President of the Kyrgyz Republic, Sadyr Japarov, with the Speaker of the Senate of the Parliament of the Republic of Kazakhstan Maulen Ashimbayev on January 24, 2023, views were exchanged on further strengthening and expanding the political-economic, cultural-human ties between the countries. The President stated that the dynamics of bilateral cooperation with Kazakhstan is at a very high level and Kyrgyzstan will make every effort to strengthen it more comprehensively. The Chairman of the Senate of the Parliament of Kazakhstan expressed his country's interest in further developing comprehensive cooperation with the Kyrgyz Republic. After the meeting, the parties expressed their confidence that the cooperation between Kyrgyzstan and Kazakhstan will continue to develop on the basis of solid allied relations and strategic partnership. [15]

Conclusion

In conclusion, the current state of relations between Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan in recent years can be considered stable and positive. Kazakhstan has historically been one of Kyrgyzstan's most important trading partners and investors. Today's relations are seen by both states as relations dominated by the desire to establish relations on a stable and predictable basis. There is also an external motivating factor for improving bilateral relations. Neither Kazakhstan nor Kyrgyzstan benefits from having their relations moderated by someone from the outside. Both states are quite capable of resolving their "fraternal differences" themselves. Kazakhstan is in a good position and the population perceives Kazakhstan as a friendly country. A reliable foundation for the formation, development and strengthening of relations between the republics of Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan is the geographical proximity of the two countries, deep historical roots, common language, culture, traditions. Therefore, the development of cooperation with the Kyrgyz state remains one of the tasks of Kazakhstan's foreign policy. The establishment of good-neighborly, stable relations with a neighboring

country is one of the important factors in ensuring the national security of the two countries.

In one of his speeches, President of Kazakhstan Nursultan Nazarbayev noted that "There are few peoples in the world whose destinies are as closely linked as the Kyrgyz and Kazakhs. A single history and kinship, the intertwining of millions of human destinies, common aspirations and goals – all this is the unshakable foundation of our joint future. This is a valuable historical heritage of our two peoples, which must be preserved and multiplied for our future generations."

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